

Identifying Key Course Units in Engineering Programs Through Grade Correlation Analysis

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15881259>

Abstract

Which course units in an engineering program are most correlated with performance in other units? Can early academic results predict future success or risk of dropout? This study analyzes final grades from a Computer Engineering program to identify correlations between course performance within and across semesters. By applying correlation analysis and network theory, we assess the centrality of key course units in influencing academic outcomes. Our findings reveal strong intra-semester correlations, particularly among courses emphasizing quantitative skills, and significant inter-semester correlations suggesting that performance in foundational subjects predicts future academic success. These insights are critical for academic management, as students with three or more failures in a single semester are held back, delaying graduation and substantially increasing dropout risks, especially among scholarship recipients. The results can guide curriculum development and inform targeted academic support strategies aimed at improving student retention and success.

Keywords: grade correlations, dropout risk, academic success, engineering education.

1 Introduction

Is there a way to predict the possibility of success of a student from his or her past grades? Is there an early warning that a student will drop out of higher education?

Predicting student success or identifying early signs of dropout in higher education has become a crucial area of research for institutions seeking to improve retention rates and academic outcomes. These issues not only affect students' personal and professional trajectories but also have broader implications for institutional credibility and funding efficiency, especially in cases involving scholarship recipients, where external stakeholders are also invested.

A comprehensive review by Kocsis and Molnár (2024), analyzing 95 studies published since 2012, highlights several reliable predictors of academic success and dropout risk. Among the most significant are prior academic performance indicators, such as Grade Point Average (GPA) or Cumulative GPA (CGPA). Demographic variables, particularly gender, with male students displaying a higher likelihood of dropping out, and non-academic factors, such as external workload, also play key roles.

Psychological and behavioral traits are equally important in predicting academic outcomes. The review points to intrinsic motivation, self-regulated learning strategies, self-efficacy, conscientiousness, and grit as substantial contributors to academic persistence and performance. These findings are echoed by Sandoval and Orfali (2024), who found that conscientiousness and concentration were positively correlated with student performance, reinforcing the role of psychological readiness and executive functioning in higher education success.

Gallego et al. (2021) conducted a cluster analysis on 284 first-year Health Sciences students at a Spanish university. Their findings indicate that students with both high cognitive skills and effective learning strategies (Cluster 1) significantly outperformed peers in GPA and credit accumulation, compared to those in Clusters 2

and 3, characterized respectively by cognitive aptitude but weak learning strategies, and low cognitive abilities with moderate strategy use. This underscores the interplay between ability and behavior in shaping academic outcomes.

From a broader institutional and policy perspective, Behr et al. (2021) explored the multidimensional causes of university dropout. They categorized influences into three tiers: macro-level (national education policy), meso-level (institutional practices and support systems), and micro-level (student-specific factors such as prior education and employment status). This layered framework offers a comprehensive lens through which dropout phenomena can be understood and addressed.

Finally, Nurmalitasari et al. (2023) identified a set of critical dropout factors specific to private universities in Central Java, Indonesia. These include financial constraints, academic dissatisfaction, low academic achievement, and the economic status of students' families. Their study highlights the urgent need for financial and academic support structures, especially in under-resourced educational contexts.

This article investigates the widely held assumption that previous academic performance serves as a reliable predictor of future success or failure in higher education. Specifically, it analyzes the final grades of students enrolled in a Computer Engineering program, aiming to identify correlations in academic performance both within the same semester (intra-semester) and across successive semesters (inter-semester).

The type of correlation being used is Pearson correlation, that establishes linear similarities between sets of data. In terms of final grades, if correlations between two sets of grades is high, then students with high grades in one set usually have high grades in the other set; conversely, students with low degrees in one set also tend to have low degrees in the other set. Low correlations indicate that there are no linear connections between grades obtained by students in one set with grades obtained by the same students in the other set. So correlations help one analyse how results in one course unit might be connected with results in other course unit.

Section 2 offers a detailed overview of the dataset, including the filtering criteria employed to ensure the reliability and consistency of the data. Section 3 presents a focused case study analyzing intra-semester correlations, providing insights into the relationships between student performance across course units within the same academic term. Section 4 explores inter-semester correlations, identifying course units whose outcomes appear to significantly influence student success in subsequent semesters. Section 5 examines potential relationships between the failure rates in courses offered during the program's second semester and the failures experienced by the same students in courses from the first semester

2 Data

The dataset used in this study comprises academic records from 687 students in the Computer Engineering program, 258 in Mechanical Engineering, and 380 in Mechatronics Engineering, after applying necessary data filtering procedures. The analysis spans nine semesters for each program, covering the academic periods of the second semester of 2023 and the first semester of 2024.

Correlations were computed using students' final grades, which reflect a weighted average of assessments including written exams, projects, quizzes, and class activities. Intra-semester correlations were calculated by selecting students who had valid final grades in all course units within a given semester. For inter-semester correlations, the analysis included only those students who had final grades in all course units for both semesters being compared. Pearson correlation was used in these analyses.

A total of 18 intra-semester correlation matrices and 8 inter-semester correlation matrices were generated for each of the three programs. Given the breadth of the dataset, this article will focus on presenting and discussing the results for the Computer Engineering program, which offers the largest sample size and most comprehensive data coverage. Section 6 presents conclusions and possibilities of further studies.

3 Intra-semester correlations

The first step in the analysis was to filter students who received final grades in a given semester. This procedure excluded a small number of students who withdrew from one or more course units before any grades were assigned.

Next, we constructed correlation matrices based on final grades to calculate intra-semester correlations. These matrices were built so that cell ij presents the correlation of final grades of course unit i with course unit j . To distinguish meaningful correlations from noise, we studied shuffled datasets where the order of the grades was randomized. From this, we observed that correlations below 0.5 are generally indistinguishable from random fluctuations. Thus, only correlations above 0.5 are considered significant in our analysis.

Data was accessed from two consecutive semesters, allowing us to build separate correlation matrices for Semester 2 of 2023 and Semester 1 of 2024. Comparing these matrices provides an estimate of the standard deviation between correlation values, which are always lower than 0.2, but most often lower than 0.1.

Tables 1, 2, and 3 show the results for the first, second and third semesters of the Computer Engineering program. Higher correlations are highlighted with boldface and larger numbers. The values presented are weighted averages across semesters, showing only the first significant digit.

Table 1. Correlations between final grades of the Course Units of the first semester.

First Semester	Software Design	Grand Challenges of Engineering	Instrumentation and Measurement	Modeling and Simulation of the Physical World	Design Nature
Software Design	1	0.4	0.6	0.6	0.2
Grand Challenges of Engineering	0.4	1	0.5	0.3	0.5
Instrumentation and Measurement	0.6	0.5	1	0.6	0.4
Modeling and Simulation of the Physical World	0.6	0.3	0.6	1	0.4
Design Nature	0.2	0.5	0.4	0.4	1

Table 2. Correlations between final grades of the Course Units of the second semester.

Second Semester	Electrical Drives	Co-Design of Apps	Data Science	Physics of Motion	Mathematics of Variation
Electrical Drives	1	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.7
Co-Design of Apps	0.6	1	0.6	0.6	0.7
Data Science	0.7	0.6	1	0.7	0.7
Physics of Motion	0.8	0.6	0.7	1	0.9
Mathematics of Variation	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.9	1

Table 3. Correlations between final grades of the Course Units of the third semester.

Third Semester	Multivariable Mathematics	Deconstructing Matter	Agile Collaborative Development	System Elements	Computational Robotics
Multivariable Mathematics	1.0	0.6	0.7	0.6	0.6
Deconstructing Matter	0.6	1.0	0.7	0.6	0.7
Agile Collaborative Development	0.7	0.7	1.0	0.7	0.8
System Elements	0.6	0.6	0.7	1.0	0.7
Computational Robotics	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.7	1.0

Since correlation matrices are symmetric, the information above and below the diagonal is redundant.

From Table 1, significant correlations are observed among Software Design, Instrumentation and Measurement, and Modeling and Simulation of the Physical World. These course units are STEM-oriented (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics), reflecting interconnected skill sets involving programming, laboratory data handling, and modeling of physical phenomena.

In contrast, Table 2 shows much stronger correlations among second-semester course units, which are also heavily STEM-based. Notably, there is a very high correlation between Physics of Motion (covering kinematics and variation) and Mathematics of Variation (focusing on calculus, differential equations, and linear algebra). This suggests that students who perform well in one of these courses are highly likely to perform well in the other, and similarly for students with lower performance.

Table 3 show sizeable correlations between all course units, be them general course units of Engineering (Multivariable Mathematics and Deconstructing Matter) or more specific course units of the Computer Engineering Program.

Analysis of subsequent semesters (fourth to ninth) reveals a similar trend: strong correlations among STEM courses in earlier semesters, gradually weakening as students progress through the program. Correlations tend to be weaker among course units of semesters above four.

4 Inter-semester correlations

Further analysis was conducted on the correlations between students' final grades in course units across consecutive semesters. To perform this analysis, we further filtered the data, selecting only students who had final grades in all course units of both semesters being compared. Since we have only one dataset per correlation matrix, we do not report means or standard deviations for these values. Additionally, we focus exclusively on correlations between different semesters, resulting in asymmetric matrices.

Tables 4 and 5 present the correlation matrices: Table 4 shows correlations between the first and second semesters of the Computer Science program, while Table 5 presents correlations between the second and third semesters. Both tables also include two additional indicators inspired by complex network theory (Newman 2010): Out Node Strength and In Node Strength. In Table 4, for instance, the Out Node Strength of a first-semester course unit represents the sum of its correlations with second-semester course units. Conversely, the

In Node Strength of a second-semester course unit captures the sum of its correlations with first-semester course units.

Table 4. Correlations between final grades of first-semester and second-semester course units.

	Electrical Drives	Co-Design of Apps	Data Science	Physics of Motion	Mathematics of Variation	Out Node Strength
Software Design	0.6	0.6	0.8	0.7	0.8	3.5
Grand Challenges of Engineering	0.7	0.7	0.6	0.5	0.6	3.1
Instrumentation and Measurement	0.7	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	3.9
Modeling and Simulation of the Physical World	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.8	0.9	3.9
Design Nature	0.4	0.7	0.3	0.4	0.4	2.2
In Node Strength	3.1	3.6	3.2	3.2	3.5	

Table 5. Correlations between final grades of second-semester and third-semester course units.

	Multivariable Mathematics	Deconstructing Matter	Agile Collaborative Development	System Elements	Computational Robotics	Out Node Strength
Electrical Drives	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.3	0.1	2.0
Co-Design of Apps	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.1	1.7
Data Science	0.4	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.2	2.3
Physics of Motion	0.9	0.6	0.7	0.5	0.2	2.9
Mathematics of Variation	0.9	0.5	0.8	0.4	0.2	2.8
In Node Strength	3.2	2.7	3.0	2.0	0.8	

From Table 4, Instrumentation and Measurement stands out with the highest Out Node Strength, closely followed by Modeling and Simulation of the Physical World. It is also worth highlighting the particularly strong correlation between Modeling and Simulation of the Physical World and Mathematics of Variation. Regarding In Node Strength, Co-Design of Apps, which is a highly project-based, user-centered course, emerges as the most impacted course unit of the second semester.

Looking at Table 5, strong correlations are evident between the second-semester units Physics of Motion and Mathematics of Variation with the third-semester unit Multivariable Mathematics. Notably, Multivariable Mathematics also has the highest In Node Strength, followed by Agile Collaborative Development, a course unit specific to Computer Engineering. Physics of Motion and Mathematics of Variation again show the highest Out Node Strengths.

According to the literature, course units with high Out Node Strength act as key determinants of student success in subsequent semesters. Students achieving high grades in these courses are more likely to perform well in following semesters. Conversely, students who underperform in these critical courses may be at higher risk of academic difficulties or even dropout, suggesting the need for early support and intervention strategies.

5 Determinants of the risk for dropout

Failures in multiple course units are among the main factors contributing to student attrition in higher education, particularly when they occur within the first two years of undergraduate programs (Cabello & Chagas, 2021; Aulck et al., 2016). Thus, the early identification of students with a high probability of failure can serve as an important tool for academic management, enabling the implementation of more effective measures to combat dropout rates, such as offering targeted academic support.

The course units offered during the second semester of the Computer Engineering program present significant challenges for a considerable portion of students, consistently showing the highest failure rates within the program (an analysis of progression to the third semester indicates a significant drop in multiple failures). Therefore, this study investigates the extent to which failures in first-semester courses influence subsequent failures in the second semester.

Table 6 presents the failure rates in second-semester courses among different groups within the studied population. Only those second-semester courses with failure rates above 5% were included in the analysis. Failure rates among students who failed Design Nature or Instrumentation and Measurement in the first semester were not analysed because none of the students in the studied group were retained in these courses.

As examples, Electrical Drives had a failure rate of 62% of the students considering the total number of students in the second semester. Of those who failed that course unit, 88% had also failed the first semester course unit Software Design. Of those who failed Electrical Devices, 100% had also failed Grand Challenges of Engineering and Modeling and Simulation of the Physical World. Difference from total indicates the difference between percent failures in a course unit of the first semester and a course unit of the second semester.

Table 6. Failed courses in the second semester compared with failed courses in the first semester of Computer Engineering.

Failed Course (second semester) →	Electrical Drives	Data Science	Physics of Motion	Mathematics of Variation
Relative to the total second-semester cohort	62%	38%	38%	24%
Among students who failed Software Design (first semester)	88%	88%	63%	63%
Among students who failed Software Design (difference from total)	(+26%)	(+50%)	(+25%)	(+39%)
Among students who failed Grand Challenges of Engineering (first semester)	100%	75%	50%	50%
Among students who failed Grand Challenges of Engineering (difference from total)	(+38%)	(+37%)	(+12%)	(+26%)
Among students who failed Modeling and Simulation of the Physical World (first semester)	100%	100%	100%	100%
Among students who failed Modeling and Simulation of the Physical World (difference from total)	(+38%)	(+62%)	(+62%)	(+76%)

The data suggest that *Modeling and Simulation of the Physical World* plays a central role in predicting failures during the second semester. In the studied cohort, every student who failed *Modeling and Simulation* subsequently failed all four second-semester courses analyzed. As this course integrates foundational concepts from Mathematics, Physics, and Programming through a project-based approach, poor performance may serve as a strong indicator that a student will struggle further in the second semester, where these concepts are addressed with a higher level of formalism.

Additionally, it is noteworthy that failure rates in *Data Science* are markedly high among students who failed *Software Design*, likely because many activities in *Data Science* demand programming skills developed in *Software Design*.

Students who fail any first-semester course and proceed to the second semester already face additional challenges, as they must balance the demands of new coursework while retaking courses they previously failed. Moreover, the findings suggest that failures in specific first-semester courses are particularly critical, highlighting the importance of targeted interventions, such as reinforcement programs, to mitigate the risk of further academic difficulties in the second semester.

6 Conclusion

This study highlights the importance of early academic performance as a predictive factor for future success or risk of dropout in Engineering programs. By analyzing correlations between final grades across the first three semesters of the Computer Engineering program, we identified specific course units that play pivotal roles in shaping students' academic trajectories.

Intra-semester analyses reveal that STEM-oriented courses, particularly those emphasizing Mathematics, Physics, and Programming, exhibit strong grade correlations, suggesting shared cognitive demands. Inter-semester analyses further demonstrate that performance in foundational courses, notably *Modeling and Simulation of the Physical World* and *Instrumentation and Measurement*, is strongly associated with success in subsequent semesters.

Moreover, the findings point to a heightened risk of academic failure in the second semester for students who struggle with key first-semester courses. In particular, students failing *Modeling and Simulation of the Physical World* exhibited substantially higher failure rates across all major second-semester course units, underscoring the need for targeted early interventions.

Identifying students at risk based on early academic indicators allows institutions to implement support strategies, such as remedial programs, tutoring, or personalized mentoring, thereby improving student retention and academic success.

Future research could expand the analysed data to cover longer time periods, allowing for an investigation into whether the observed patterns persist across different cohorts. We have data for all semesters of the Engineering courses and could use them.

Additionally, they could include students from Mechanical and Mechatronics Engineering programs, enabling a comparison with the results from Computer Engineering. Finally, such studies could assess the effectiveness of interventions aimed at mitigating the effects of failures in first-semester courses.

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